

THE URBAN DESIGN CODE IS A SET OF RULES AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE DESIGN OF SIGNS AND OUTDOOR ADVERTISING, HISTORICAL BUILDING FACADES AND ADJACENT AREAS

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Abstract. *The design code defines the main design elements, which are the most important for each specific area. The design code encourages architects and planners to find creative solutions according to the basic design elements defined for a particular environment to meet the requirements defined as essential.*

Keywords: *design code, standards, graphic rules, graphic elements, guidelines, master plan, components, urban design code.*

Аннотация. *Дизайн код определяет основные элементы дизайна, которые являются наиболее важными для каждой конкретной области. Дизайн код побуждает архитекторов и планировщиков находить творческие решения, в соответствии с основными элементами дизайна, определенными для конкретной среды, чтобы соответствовать требованиям, определенным как существенные.*

Ключевые слова: *нормы проектирования, стандарты, графические правила, графические элементы, рекомендации, ген.план, компоненты, градостроительные нормы.*

A design code is a set of rules, norms and requirements that define how a particular city should look to planners and other interested parties - a model set of outdoor advertising, building facades, signs and colors.

The design code establishes regulations pertaining to the placement, dimensions, and aesthetic characteristics of signage, with the objective of ensuring that they do not overwhelm the building in question, but rather become integrated into the urban fabric and serve to accentuate the architectural features of the city. It is a comprehensive set of illustrated design requirements that delineates precise and detailed parameters. The graphic and written components of a code for the physical development of a site or area should be based on a design vision, such as that set forth in a master plan or other design and development framework for the area. This vision is informed by the spatial master plan or other urban design proposals, and the code describes the rules through words and graphics.

Design is important in presenting an exclusive design. As a result of recent reforms, the government has ensured that good design and planning work are not mutually exclusive, and has set the rules for creating quality good areas on the ground. Design codes can play an important role in driving these reforms by applying them to continuous quality improvement.

Design codes are a reliable form of design guidance. Developed with the right skills and experience, and effectively used, design codes are key to achieving one of the key objectives for the new housing planning policy, which is to ensure that all housing is well designed and built to a high standard[1].

Design Codes provides practical and practical advice, local authorities, developers and other key stakeholders on how to prepare and use design codes effectively.

The urban design code comprises a set of rules and recommendations pertaining to the aesthetic aspects of signage and outdoor advertising, as well as the design of historical building facades and adjacent areas. It encourages owners and tenants of establishments to adhere to the same design of establishment names, information boards and storefronts on the facades of buildings to which the design code applies.

Design codes are one of the open options for local authorities and designers to achieve high quality and good place design [2]. Although this is not the only option, if used effectively it reflects local needs and provides greater opportunities for local authorities and designers to achieve transparent, streamlined and collaborative quality design.

Over time, more design teams will adopt this new approach and help develop knowledge of how to use this flexible tool to achieve a quality urban environment. The following are basic definitions of design codes:

- Design codes are a new approach to improving design quality. They help to design the best design in advance by investing resources to simplify further processes.
- Design codes are a special form of detailed design guidance that contains a set of written and graphic rules that clearly define the two and three-dimensional design elements of a particular development or area.
- Provisions in design codes are technical and precise. They guide (and sometimes advise) the user about the physical components of a place.
- Design codes are a means of delivery. To be effective, they must be based on a clear vision of the project for the site or area.
- Extensive evidence demonstrates their potential to improve design quality and provide a more defined, streamlined and coordinated manufacturing process.
- Design codes confirm cultural changes in design and the shift to a spatial approach to design.

No one sets out to design and create poorly designed, characterless spaces. However, many of the areas being developed today continue to exhibit these characteristics. Recent large-scale trials in England have shown that design codes have significant potential to help address these challenges by serving to ensure the creation of high-quality districts in a more efficient and effective way. Some of the potential benefits of design codes include:

- Developing a broader environmental project for small producers at the local level.
- The positive sense of place and high economic value that quality design can bring.
- A more accurate planning process, taking into account a clear climate for investment.
- Simplifying development controls, which saves time and money for developers and local authorities.
- A more coordinated development process based on consensus instead of confrontation.

Design codes are a special form of detailed design guidance. A design code is a set of written and graphic rules that precisely establish how the two and three-dimensional design elements of a given project or area relate to each other without defining the overall result.

The purpose of a design code is to specify the items that constitute an acceptable design solution for a particular area or site, thereby providing a level of certainty for developers and the local community [3].

Design codes define design principles aimed at providing better quality places, such as requirements for streets, blocks, boulevards, etc., or they may focus on landscape, architectural or building performance issues (such as improving energy efficiency). However, unlike many general

urban design guidelines or local development standards, design codes do not simply reproduce rules or guidelines found in other national or local policy or guidance documents. Instead, codes make a positive statement about the specific characteristics of a place. Codes focus on design features that are important to achieve and establish and reliably record design elements that "must be". In this way, codes help ensure continuity in quality and consistency over time[4].

To achieve this purpose, design codes often need to be based on the design concept of the master plan or the appearance of another place or area. Sometimes they can go beyond the scope of design and drafting. In both cases, the set of design guidelines that make up design codes reflect the specific requirements of a location.

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